

Studies on Antiinflammatory Activity among a Series of Substituted Indan Acids. Part-III

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Manuscript received 20 February 1985, accepted 11 September 1985

Significant antiinflammatory activity observed among indan-1-acids coupled with their low toxicity prompted synthesis of some newer analogues with longer aliphatic chain or even branched chain structure to impart greater lipophilicity and better transport facility through biomembrane. Among the long chain compounds so synthesised, indan acetic acids and propionic acids showed better activity profile and maximum activity was observed in methoxy substituted acids.

INDAN acids which belong to the class of aryl-alkanoic acids were reported to possess significant antiinflammatory activity by a number of workers¹⁻⁸. A number of indan acids were synthesised, screened and extensively investigated in our laboratory^{4,5}. The present work is designed to get a better and safer antiinflammatory agent by chain expansion of the potent indan acids. This will lower their acidity and increase their lipophilicity. Since ulcerogenicity is associated with carboxyl function and is almost inseparable, the lowering of acidity may result in a less ulcerogenic compound. Long chain indan acid analogues were synthesised by consecutive Arndt-Estert synthesis starting with the corresponding indan-1-acetic acids. These acids were screened for their acute antiinflammatory activity in carragenin induced rat paw-edema model.

- 1 n=0; X=Y=H
- 2 n=1; X=Y=H
- 3 n=2; X=Y=H
- 4 n=3; X=Y=H
- 5 n=0; X=OCH₃; Y=H
- 6 n=1; X=OCH₃; Y=H
- 7 n=2; X=OCH₃; Y=H
- 8 n=3; X=OCH₃; Y=H
- 9 n=0; X=Y=OCH₃
- 10 n=1; X=Y=OCH₃
- 11 n=2; X=Y=OCH₃
- 12 n=3; X=Y=OCH₃

Experimental

Melting points were determined in a Gallenkamp apparatus and are uncorrected. The structures were supported by elemental analysis and infrared

spectrum. All the indan-1-acids showed characteristic ir peak at 1650-1700 cm⁻¹ (COOH).

Indan-1-acetic acids⁴ were synthesised by cyclodehydration of the corresponding phenylglutaric acids⁷ in polyphosphoric acid followed by Clemmensen reduction while indan-1-carboxylic acids⁹ were synthesised from the corresponding phenylsuccinic acids⁸ by cyclodehydration and Clemmensen reduction.

Indan-1-acetyl chloride (2a): A mixture of indan-1-acetic acid (2; 8.8 g, 0.05 mol) and thionyl chloride (0.06 mol) in dry benzene was refluxed for 1 h. Indan-1-acetyl chloride⁹ (8.5 g) was distilled at 120° (1.5 mm).

β-(1-Indanyl)propionic acid (3): **2a** (9.2 g, 0.05 mol) was dissolved in dry ether (20 ml) and added slowly to a cold ethereal solution of diazomethane (prepared from 42.6 g nitrosomethylurea¹⁰) under reflux. The mixture was stirred continuously and kept below 5° during the addition, and allowed to stand overnight at room temperature. Ether was distilled off under reduced pressure. The indan-1-acetyl diazoketone (9.8 g) was dissolved in absolute methanol (400 ml), and a slurry of silver oxide (prepared from 6.8 g AgNO₃ and 3.8 g NaOH) in methanol was added in portions at 30-40°, and the course of the reaction was followed by the nitrogen evolution. After the addition was over, temperature of the bath was raised to 60-80° and the mixture was refluxed for 0.5 h. The solution was boiled with charcoal, filtered and the alcoholic solution concentrated. The resulting ester was extracted in ether, washed consecutively with dilute acid, alkali and water, dried and distilled under reduced pressure. The product⁹ was distilled at 130-135° (2-3 mm) (9.8 g, 96%), η_D²⁰ 1.5174 (Found: C, 76.28; H, 7.91. C₁₃H₁₆O₃ calcd. C, 76.47; H, 7.84%). The ester (9.0 g, 0.044 mol) was refluxed with 10% alcoholic KOH solution (50 ml) for 3 h. Alcohol was removed and the aqueous layer washed with ether and the resulting β-(1-indanyl)propionic acid⁹ was precipitated with calculated amount of dilute

HCl. Precipitated acid upon keeping solidified and was crystallised from hydroalcoholic solvent, m.p. 51-53° (Found : C, 75.52; H, 7.54. C₁₂H₁₄O₂ calcd. C, 75.79 H, 7.37%).

β-1-(Indan)propionyl chloride (3a) : 3 (9.5 g, 0.05 mol) was refluxed with thionyl chloride (0.1 mol) in dry benzene for 1 h. The acid chloride distilled at 96-98° (1 mm) as a colourless oil (86%).

γ-(1-Indanyl)butyric acid (4) : 3a was reacted with diazomethane in the same molar ratio as mentioned under 3 and the ester was obtained as the fraction distilled at 98-100° (1 mm) (94%), η²⁰ 1.5192 (Found : C, 76.84; H, 8.52. C₁₄H₁₈O₂ calcd. C, 77.06; H, 8.26%). The ester upon saponification with alcoholic alkali yielded 4 (86%), b.p. 110-115° (1-2 mm); η²⁰ 1.5279 (Found : C, 76.32; H, 7.91. C₁₈H₁₈O₂ calcd. C, 76.47; H, 7.84%).

6-Methoxyindan-1-acetyl chloride (6a) : A mixture of 6 and thionyl chloride (1 : 1.2 mol) was refluxed for 30 min. The product distilled at 142-145° (1.5 mm).

β-(6-Methoxy-1-indanyl)propionic acid (7) : 6a was reacted with diazomethane in the same molar ratio as described earlier and the ester was obtained as the fraction distilled at 150-155° (1-2 mm) (97%), η²⁰ 1.5259 (Found : C, 71.54; H, 7.81. C₁₄H₁₈O₃ calcd. C, 71.79; H, 7.69%). The ester upon saponification yielded 7, m.p. 69-71° (Found : C, 71.24; H, 7.08. C₁₈H₁₈O₃ calcd. C, 70.91; H, 7.27%).

β-(6-Methoxyindan-1-)propionyl chloride (7a) : 7 was refluxed with thionyl chloride (1 : 2 mol) in dry

benzene for 30 min and 7a was distilled at 115-119° (1 mm).

γ-(6-Methoxy-1-indanyl)butyric acid (8) : 7a was reacted with diazomethane in the same molar ratio as mentioned earlier and the *γ*-(6-methoxy-1-indanyl)-methyl butyrate was obtained as the fraction distilled at 145-150° (0.5 mm) (89%), η²⁰ 1.5199 (Found : C, 72.21; H, 8.41. C₁₈H₂₀O₃ calcd. C, 72.58; H, 8.06%). The ester upon saponification yielded 8 distilled at 178-180° (0.1 mm) η²⁰ 1.5361 (Found : C, 71.92; H, 7.98. C₁₄H₁₈O₃ calcd. C, 71.79; H, 7.69%).

5,6-Dimethoxyindan-1-acetyl chloride (10a) : A mixture of 5,6-dimethoxyindan-1-acetic acid⁶ (10) and thionyl chloride (1 : 1.2 mol) in dry benzene was refluxed for 15 min. Thionyl chloride was removed and the acid chloride being thermolabile was used as such without further purification.

β-(5,6-Dimethoxy-1-indanyl)propionic acid (11) : 10a was reacted with diazomethane in the same molar proportion as described earlier and the resulting methyl ester was distilled at 175-179° (0.5 mm) (85%), η²⁰ 1.5285 (Found : C, 68.42; H, 7.48. C₁₈H₂₀O₄ calcd. C, 68.18; H, 7.76%). The ester upon saponification yielded 11, m.p. 138-139° (Found : C, 67.02; H, 7.26. calcd. C, 67.2; H, 7.2%).

β-(5,6-Dimethoxyindan-1-)propionyl chloride (11a) : 11 was treated with thionyl chloride as described earlier and was used without further purification.

γ-(5,6-Dimethoxy-1-indanyl)butyric acid (12) : 11a was treated with diazomethane in the same

TABLE I—ANTIINFLAMMATORY ACTIVITY OF INDAN-1-ACIDS

Compd. no.	Dose p.o. mg/kg	% Increase in paw volume (mean ± SE)*			
		2 h**	3 h	4 h	24 h
1	200	67.94 ± 3.63 (20.63) ^a	82.01 ± 4.54 (28.89)	98.24 ± 4.91 (19.46)	87.1 ± 6.69
2	200	51.00 ± 4.58 (40.42)	61.50 ± 3.93 (42.88)	79.55 ± 4.46 (39.62)	82.9 ± 5.21 (5.14)
3	200	52.24 ± 4.31 (38.97)	64.45 ± 4.19 (40.14)	75.92 ± 4.92 (38.25)	81.5 ± 5.48 (6.75)
4	200	61.18 ± 4.63 (28.53)	75.16 ± 5.36 (80.19)	86.80 ± 5.01 (28.84)	86.8 ± 5.52 (1.2)
5	200	52.29 ± 3.84 (38.91)	64.48 ± 4.62 (40.11)	76.56 ± 4.81 (37.23)	74.09 ± 3.16 (15.23)
6	200	39.71 ± 2.81 (53.61)	48.21 ± 3.11 (55.22)	56.87 ± 3.21 (53.38)	59.26 ± 1.68 (15.23)
7	200	40.16 ± 2.66 (53.08)	48.58 ± 2.99 (54.91)	58.74 ± 2.63 (51.81)	61.18 ± 1.15 (30.00)
8	200	45.92 ± 4.38 (46.35)	55.86 ± 4.51 (49.12)	65.61 ± 5.39 (46.21)	71.03 ± 3.58 (13.17)
9	200	50.58 ± 4.63 (41.18)	60.77 ± 5.24 (43.56)	78.59 ± 4.11 (39.67)	79.21 ± 2.96 (16.23)
10	200	37.51 ± 3.91 (56.18)	45.19 ± 3.63 (58.02)	53.95 ± 2.81 (55.77)	56.88 ± 1.16 (34.92)
11	200	38.36 ± 3.51 (55.32)	45.71 ± 2.88 (57.54)	57.04 ± 3.51 (53.24)	60.21 ± 1.33 (31.11)
12	200	42.37 ± 4.91 (49.91)	51.48 ± 3.88 (52.18)	62.76 ± 4.61 (48.55)	69.68 ± 4.58 (20.27)
Peaynlyb- tazone	100	43.57 ± 3.18 (49.10)	57.9 ± 4.52 (46.22)	72.56 ± 4.32 (40.51)	68.39 ± 4.58 (21.84)
Indometh- acin (i.p.)	8	54.58	45.23	36.05	22.27
Saline (Control)		85.6 ± 3.16	107.67 ± 3.98	121.98 ± 3.88	87.4 ± 3.35

* Values are average of 6 animals.

** Time after carragenin administration.

^a Percent inhibition of edema.

molar ratio as mentioned earlier and the resulting γ -(5,6-dimethoxy-1-indanyl)methyl butyrate was obtained as the fraction distilled at 181-185° (0.5 mm) (79%), η^{25} 1.5211 (Found: C, 69.43; H, 7.63. $C_{16}H_{22}O_4$ calcd. C, 69.06; H, 7.91%). The ester upon saponification yielded **12**, m.p. 102-103° (Found: C, 68.34; H, 7.48. $C_{16}H_{20}O_4$ calcd. C, 68.18; H, 7.76%).

Antiinflammatory screening: Screening for antiinflammatory activity was done in carragenin induced rat paw-edema model of Winter *et al.*¹¹. Male albino rats of wister strain weighing 120-160 g were used after acclimatisation for 8 days to the laboratory condition. The initial paw volumes were determined upto a fixed mark by mercury displacement technique¹² which was measured by a travelling microscope. The compounds were administered by oral route dissolved in aq. alkali (pH 7.6 ± 0.4) 1 h before carragenin administration (0.1 ml of 1% solution in normal saline) into the planter surface of the right hind paw. The paw volumes were determined at an hourly interval up to 4 h and at 24 h. Percent inhibition of paw edema was compared using the formula,

$$\text{Inhibition} = \frac{V_c - V_t}{V_c} \times 100$$

where, V_c and V_t are average edema volumes of control and treated group, respectively. The screening data is presented in Table 1. The activity of the compounds was compared with those of phenylbutazone and indomethacin⁴.

Results and Discussion

From the results of carragenin induced rat paw-edema test, it is evident that there is a definite

gradation of activity profile among the acid series. Indiscriminate chain lengthening is not beneficial for biological activity, as the activity seems to reside in a small structural framework. Antiinflammatory activity is more prominent in indan-1-acetic and indan-1-propionic acids, the carboxylic and butyric acids shows less activity. Biological activity in this series may be potentiated by incorporating methoxyl substitution at 5 and 6 positions. Onset of action of these compounds are relatively slow, compared to phenylbutazone. The antiinflammatory activity reached its peak after 3 h of their oral administration and in some cases retained even after 24 h. All these findings necessitate further intensive pharmacological evaluation and toxicity studies of potent acids and work in this direction is in progress.

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